

MOTIVATIONS, TRAINING OUTCOMES, AND CLINICAL PRACTICE CHARACTERISTICS OF NORTH AMERICAN CHIROPRACTORS: A CROSS-SECTIONAL SURVEY

Gannon Brochin, DC, MS¹, Marc T. Edwards, MD, MBA^{1,2}

ABSTRACT

Objective: To describe chiropractors' motivations for training, perceived training outcomes, and current practice characteristics in a North American respondent sample, and to explore associations with practice orientation and selected clinical behaviors.

Methods: Cross-sectional, web-based survey of licensed and retired chiropractors in the U.S. and Canada recruited via professional organizations. The instrument included 7-point end-anchored items on motivations, training outcomes, and practice characteristics. Practice orientation subgroups were defined a priori based on subluxation definitions ("Do not use," "Biomechanical/modern," "Vitalistic"). Nonparametric analyses included Kruskal-Wallis with Dwass-Steel-Critchlow-Flinger (DSCF) pairwise post hoc testing, Spearman's ρ , and Wilcoxon signed-rank tests.

Results: Of 330 responses, 303 completed at least one outcome block and were included in analysis. Motivations were predominantly prosocial and meaning-oriented with low endorsement of status or extrinsic motives. Training outcomes were strongest for clinical reasoning, communication, and lifestyle counseling. Practice characteristics included high autonomy, adequate visit time, and reliance on history and physical examination over routine testing. Practice orientation tracked behavior: higher manipulation frequency among

"Vitalistic" respondents and lower new-patient x-ray use among "Do not use" and "Biomechanical" respondents ($\rho=0.25$ and -0.31 , respectively; both $p<0.001$), with lower education satisfaction among more biomedically aligned respondents ($\rho=-0.27$, $p<0.001$). Current health did not differ from pre-training health ($p=0.84$) but was associated with current stress levels ($p<0.001$).

Conclusion: Our chiropractor sample's purpose-driven motivation profile aligns with reported strengths in reasoning, counseling, and communication within time-rich, autonomous practice settings. Pairing meaning-centered recruitment and curricula with rigorous evidence-based practice and communication training provides actionable inputs for recruitment messaging, curricular emphasis, professional development, and imaging stewardship initiatives. Findings are limited by nonprobability sampling, self-report, and cross-sectional design. Probability and longitudinal studies are warranted. (*J Contemporary Chiropr* 2026;9:171-184)

Key Indexing Terms: Chiropractic; Survey Research; Practice Patterns; Motivation

INTRODUCTION

Understanding why clinicians choose specific training pathways is an important aspect for training future clinicians. Motivation shapes learners' engagement, learning strategies, persistence, and well-being, which in turn influence training outcomes and downstream practice behaviors in health professions education. (1,2) Within self-determination theory, higher autonomous (i.e., intrinsic) motivation is consistently associated

¹ Department of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation, The University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill, Chapel Hill, NC; ² Department of Physiology and Health, Maharishi International University, Fairfield, IA

with deeper learning, higher academic performance, greater persistence, and better well-being. These are outcomes that are directly relevant to preparing clinicians for evidence-based, patient-centered care. (3) Across mainstream medicine more broadly, systematic reviews show that students' career-choice motivations commonly include altruism, interest in health care, prestige, job security, and personal or family influences, with variation by context, country, and income level. (4) These patterns underscore why clarifying profession-specific motivation profiles is important for tailoring recruitment and curricular design to optimize learning and professional development. (1,3)

Motivation profiles may differ in complementary and integrative health professions, where training often emphasizes holism and self-management. Past motivation-associated work in these health professions shows a stark contrast when compared to mainstream medicine with desires for self-healing, improved knowledge, and self-empowerment being identified as significant motivators. (5,6) These include alignment with holistic philosophies, desire to expand skills, improve outcomes, and reduce practitioner fatigue. This suggests that motivations shape both training experiences and practice patterns in hands-on, non-pharmacologic disciplines. (7,8) Notably, within the chiropractic literature to date, explicit assessment of self-oriented motives such as "self-healing" appears uncommon, representing a gap given emerging interest in how clinician well-being and personal health practices interact with training and patient care. (9)

Chiropractic occupies an important role in conservative, nonpharmacological management of neuromusculoskeletal complaints. (10,11) However, the empirical literature on motivations remains limited and is often focused on students or produces practitioner profiles that are incomplete and difficult to draw conclusions from. Several cross-sectional studies of chiropractic students reported that the desire to help others, prior personal experience with chiropractic, and attraction to a holistic, non-pharmacologic approach were prominent drivers of degree choice. (9,12) International surveys also suggest that chiropractic students hold generally positive attitudes toward evidence-based practice (EBP), positioning motivation as a plausible lever for strengthening EBP uptake during training and putting it into practice. (13) Correspondingly, chiropractic curricula that explicitly embed EBP training have demonstrated improvements in knowledge, skills, and attitudes, highlighting a link between educational design, learner engagement, and measurable training

outcomes. (14) Among practicing chiropractors, surveys from Sweden and South Africa point to favorable EBP attitudes but variable implementation, emphasizing the need to understand how earlier motivational profiles might relate to subsequent professional behaviors and continuing education engagement. (15,16) Probability-sampled surveys have established that North American chiropractors sort into distinct orientation subgroups ranging from biomedically integrated to traditionally aligned and that these subgroups differ in clinical ideology, beliefs, and practice patterns. (17-19) Prior work has also linked teaching institution background to downstream practice characteristics among Canadian chiropractors, suggesting that training context shapes the orientation a practitioner ultimately adopts. (20) Yet whether these orientation differences trace back to earlier training motivations and perceived outcomes remains unexplored.

Taken together, these data indicate that characterizing chiropractors' training motivations and examining their relationships with salient training outcomes and practice characteristics is needed. Less is known about whether motivations persist or evolve once in practice and how chiropractors rate their training outcomes and describe their practice characteristics. This is both timely and actionable for educational design and workforce development. (1,16)

This paper focuses specifically on chiropractors, aiming to delineate motivation profiles, including underexplored self-oriented motives, and to relate these profiles to training experiences and outcomes relevant to evidence-based, person-centered neuromusculoskeletal care. Few studies have examined training motivations, outcomes, and practice characteristics of chiropractors within the same framework.

The aim of this study was to gain a greater understanding of the motivations, practice characteristics, and training outcomes of chiropractors. Secondarily, we hypothesized that practice orientation would form distinguishable categories along a biomedical-to-traditional continuum and would be associated with selected practice behaviors.

METHODS

Survey Data Collection

We conducted a cross-sectional, web-based survey of healthcare professionals representing many professions

across biomedical and complementary and integrative practices to characterize (1) motivations for entering the profession, (2) perceived training outcomes, and (3) current practice characteristics from September 2024 – May 2025. This report only presents data from the chiropractic respondents. The study protocol and instrument were reviewed by the University of North Carolina Institutional Review Board (#24-1367), and participation was anonymous with consent implied by survey completion; the questionnaire header stated the study purpose, confidentiality, and an estimated completion time. We report this survey in accordance with the Consensus-Based Checklist for Reporting of Survey Studies (CROSS). (21)

The target population was licensed and retired chiropractors in the United States and Canada. We recruited via 5 professional gatekeepers consisting of state chiropractic associations (3) and chiropractic education program alumni groups (2) who distributed a standardized email invitation containing the survey link to their membership lists. The research team did not directly contact individual members and did not receive membership rosters. No monetary incentives were offered.

The survey data was collected via the online Qualtrics (Qualtrics International Inc., USA) platform using the English language. The Qualtrics platform allows for adaptive display and skip logic to tailor survey items (e.g., those not in active practice received items to identify the reasons). While the core architecture followed a standardized format for all professions, separate forms were deployed for each that included profession-specific questions.

The instrument relied on 7-point end-anchored unipolar scales mapped to 3 primary constructs: motivations for becoming a chiropractic physician, training outcomes, and current practice characteristics. Additional items addressed self-rated health, stress, modalities offered, referral patterns, new-patient volume, visit time, telehealth, ownership, and basic demographics (age, sex, location, rurality). Chiropractic-specific items addressed practice orientation along a spectrum from biomedically integrated to “vitalistic” chiropractic, enabling a planned profession-specific subgroup analyses. (17,19) The motivation, practice characteristics, and training outcome items were adapted from prior published work where scales demonstrated adequate reliability. (22-26) Chiropractic-specific items addressing subluxation orientation, manipulation frequency, and imaging practices were newly developed for this study based on constructs

identified in prior literature. (17-20) Prior to initiating data collection, three independent active practitioners and a non-participating state association board were consulted on the content of the survey for relevance to the profession and clarity of constructs with feedback being used to refine these new chiropractic-specific items. However, formal content validity testing was not conducted.

For interpretation, motivation items ranged from 1 (“Not Important”) to 7 (“Most Important”), training outcome items from 1 (“Not My Experience”) to 7 (“Exactly My Experience”), and practice characteristic items from 1 (“Not At All Like Me”) to 7 (“Exactly Like Me”). Scores of 6-7 were considered high endorsement, 3-5 mid-range, and 1-2 low endorsement. For descriptive presentation of results, items were grouped into thematic domains by the authors based on item content. These groupings were not derived from a prior taxonomy or factor structure. To characterize the internal consistency of the domain groupings, Cronbach’s α was computed for each full outcome block and for each thematic sub-domain grouping using complete-case analysis. A preliminary exploratory factor analysis (principal components extraction with varimax rotation, eigenvalue > 1 retention criterion) was conducted on each block to evaluate the empirical structure underlying the thematic groupings. The full wording of the survey and response options are provided in Supplement 1.

To eliminate breakoffs and protect against low-quality responses, responses were accepted for analysis only if a primary outcome block was answered without straight-lining (i.e., selecting the same response value for all items within a block). We also utilized the Qualtrics’ anti-ballot-box-stuffing measures to flag duplicate entries from the same device. The survey captured no direct identifiers such as IP address or geolocation. Responses were anonymized by the platform.

The study used a convenience sample of organization-recruited volunteers. Design weights require a known sampling frame and population-level demographic benchmarks against which to adjust; neither a comprehensive chiropractic licensure registry nor a validated demographic reference distribution for the North American chiropractic workforce is available at this time, precluding their application. Invitations were distributed by participating organizations via an anonymous survey link, and recipient counts were not available to the research team; therefore, a response rate could not be calculated. Analyses are therefore

presented as descriptive estimates of the responding sample.

Statistical Analysis

The primary outcomes are reported with mean and total respondents at each level of the scales, sorted by mean from high-to-low. Analyses used a complete-case approach at the outcome-block level. Respondents were included in the analytic dataset if they completed at least one of the 3 main outcome blocks (motivations for training, perceived training outcomes, or current practice characteristics). Respondents who did not complete any of these blocks were excluded. For block-specific analyses, we included only respondents who completed that block; respondents who partially completed a block were excluded from analyses of that block. Missing data occurred primarily as survey non-completion at the block level rather than selective item non-response within blocks. Each outcome table reports the number of respondents who completed that block. We did not observe obvious differences in block completion by respondent characteristics. Proportion-based items (e.g., new-patient x-ray rate) were recoded to midpoint values for continuous analysis using the scheme shown in Table 1.

Chiropractic Subgroup Comparisons

Practice orientation subgroups were defined a priori using a single item assessing subluxation use: "Which statement best describes how you define chiropractic subluxation?" Response options defined 3 subgroups along a biomedical-to-vitalistic continuum: (1) Do not use – "I don't use the term 'subluxation'"; (2) Biomechanical/ Modern – "A functional spinal joint dysfunction that may contribute to pain or impaired movement"; and (3) Vitalistic – "A misalignment of the vertebrae, which interferes with nerve function and innate healing, leading to dis-ease." This operated as a pragmatic, self-identified proxy for practice orientation based on a single item, rather than as latent or exhaustive 'types' of chiropractors. This 3-category operationalization aligns with prior surveys characterizing ideological subgroups among North American chiropractors. (17-19) We used Kruskal-Wallis tests with epsilon-squared (ϵ^2) effect sizes. Dwass-Steel-Critchlow-Fligner (DSCF) pairwise tests provided multiplicity-controlled post-hoc comparisons. Monotonic associations with ordered variables (e.g., orientation or percent-category codes) used Spearman's ρ due to non-normality.

Within-Person Analyses

For paired items, such as current health vs. health before studying the profession, we tested within-person differences using Wilcoxon signed-rank tests with rank-biserial r . To assess whether change differed by subluxation orientation, the individual difference score was analyzed across the 3 subgroups via 1-way ANOVA with Tukey-Kramer post-hoc tests.

Assumptions and Effect Sizes

For ANOVA models, we examined residual plots for approximate normality and homoscedasticity. When assumptions were materially violated, results were checked with Kruskal-Wallis tests as sensitivity analyses. Because outcomes were ordinal and distributions were non-normal, we used nonparametric tests for primary analyses.

We summarize degrees of freedom (χ^2) and p-values for Kruskal-Wallis, ρ and p for Spearman testing, W and p (with rank-biserial r) for Wilcoxon, and ϵ^2 as the effect size, interpreted as the proportion of variance explained by rank. ϵ^2 effect sizes were defined a priori with Cohen-style benchmarks: <0.06 being small, <0.14 being medium, and >0.14 being large. All tests were 2-sided with $\alpha=0.05$. No adjustment for multiple comparisons was applied and all findings should be interpreted as exploratory and hypothesis-generating rather than confirmatory. Analyses were conducted in JMP Pro 17.2 (SAS Institute, USA) and corroborated as needed in R (v4.4.2).

Results

A total of 330 responses were started. After applying exclusion criteria, 303 respondents were eligible for analysis. No respondents were excluded for straight-lining or ballot-box-stuffing; 27 were excluded for not completing any main outcome block. Most respondents were male (70%), in active practice (95%), practiced in the United States (96%), were practice owners (72%), and practiced in non-rural settings (79%). New patient visit time averaged 41 minutes, with 30 patient-contact hours per week and monthly visit volumes around 272 visits. Average completion time of the survey was 28.2 minutes. Sample characteristic information is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Chiropractic sample characteristics: 1-7 adjectival scale; Percent categories with midpoint coding: None/0%=0, <20%=10, 20-40%=30, 40-60%=50, 60-80%=70, >80%=90. DC = Doctor of Chiropractic

Characteristic	n	% or Mean (SD)
Gender: Male	212	70.0
Active practice: Yes	289	95.4
Rural practice: Yes	64	21.1
Country: United States	291	96.0
No Specialty Certification	103	31.1
Practice Owner	218	71.9
New patient visit time (minutes)	303	40.7(37.6, 43.9)
Patient contact hours per week	303	30.3(28.6, 31.9)
Monthly visit volume (visit #)	303	272.0(197.2, 346.8)
Satisfaction with DC education (1-7 adjectival scale)	303	5.1(1.3)
New patients receiving spinal X-rays (% category, midpoint-coded)	297	33.9% (31.1%)
Frequency of manipulation treatment (% category, midpoint-coded)	298	83.5% (14.2%)

Internal consistency of the 3 primary outcome blocks was acceptable to excellent. The motivation block demonstrated excellent overall consistency ($\alpha = 0.904$; $n = 286$; $k = 34$ items); thematic sub-domain α values ranged from 0.601(Extrinsic/Status) to 0.878(Self-Oriented/Wellness). The training outcomes block demonstrated good overall consistency ($\alpha = 0.865$; $n = 209$; $k = 11$ items), with sub-domain α values ranging from 0.646(Spiritual/Emotional Support) to 0.761(Clinical/Professional Competency). The practice characteristics block demonstrated acceptable overall consistency ($\alpha = 0.756$; $n = 280$; $k = 20$ items); sub-domain α values were lower (range 0.163-0.514), consistent with the block's intentionally heterogeneous coverage of distinct practice dimensions rather than a single latent construct. A preliminary exploratory factor analysis broadly supported the thematic groupings: the 34-item motivation block yielded 8 factors explaining 61.8% of variance, with dominant loadings corresponding to the proposed thematic domains; the 11-item training outcomes block yielded 2 factors (55.1% of variance) distinguishing clinical/professional from holistic/wellness competency clusters; and the 20-item practice characteristics block yielded 7 factors (63.3% of variance), further confirming the empirical heterogeneity of that domain.

Across 33 motivation items (median item mean

4.77), the highest-rated domains were prosocial and meaning-oriented (Table 2). The top items by mean were "Meaningful work," "Help others," "Potential to make a difference in the world," "Make a positive impact on my community," and "Gain a deep understanding of health." Intellectual/biomedical interests also rated highly (e.g., "Interest in complementary or integrative medicine," "Intellectual stimulation"). Extrinsic/status-oriented items were lowest (e.g., "Unable to get into medical school," "Social status," and "Prestige"). Security-oriented items were moderate-low. The summary of all motivation items appears in Table 2.

Table 2. Motivations for Chiropractic training; Analytic $n = 303$, sorted by mean from high to low

Item	Not Important	2	3	4	5	6	Most Important	Mean
Help others	2	0	2	11	34	73	181	6.36
Meaningful work	3	2	3	16	50	94	139	6.08
Make a positive impact on my community	8	4	12	28	59	86	106	5.67
Interest in science	8	9	10	29	56	99	95	5.59
Potential to make a difference in the world	16	4	17	24	70	70	106	5.48
Potential for professional independence	15	8	9	44	63	80	87	5.35
Gain a deep understanding of health	15	9	13	39	63	84	83	5.32
Intellectual stimulation	8	10	13	49	71	84	70	5.29
Interest in complementary or integrative medicine	25	11	14	41	64	75	74	5.07
Good income potential	7	12	19	52	99	74	44	5.03
Financial security	13	9	20	63	88	72	42	4.92
Help family or friends	34	18	22	43	57	63	69	4.75
Prior experience with Chiropractic	44	21	15	34	39	80	72	4.74
Stay healthy	31	20	25	55	62	54	59	4.62
Potential for flexible work hours	37	27	17	38	68	62	54	4.57
Job security	33	17	31	66	62	45	50	4.45
Make better choices in diet, nutrition, lifestyle, etc.	40	19	33	56	59	47	50	4.37
Change or develop a career	69	24	20	41	45	48	58	4.13

Dissatisfaction with conventional medicine	57	25	26	52	57	42	48	4.12
Influence of a role model	68	26	29	44	58	37	44	3.93
Improve my health	59	34	30	48	55	43	37	3.92
A 'calling' or inner awakening	84	37	22	36	30	34	61	3.78
Prior experience with illness	106	33	19	34	41	38	35	3.41
Potential for teaching	86	38	40	49	47	28	18	3.29
Heal myself	106	37	32	43	32	23	31	3.17
Influence of family/friends	101	38	33	41	44	32	16	3.16
Prestige	98	40	47	60	40	12	8	2.91
Influence of a trusted authority, spiritual leader, etc.	125	38	29	28	42	22	20	2.9
Social status	96	46	41	67	37	12	7	2.89
Grow spiritually	138	43	28	39	23	14	21	2.65
Potential to do research	116	58	41	39	32	11	8	2.6
Less physically demanding work	150	57	30	43	17	4	4	2.17
Unable to gain entry to medical school	259	15	12	5	3	6	6	1.43

The average item mean for training outcomes was 4.36 (Table 3). Highest-rated outcomes reflected core clinical and communication competencies: "It helped me identify the root cause of patients' problems," "It gave me confidence in advising patients about diet, nutrition & lifestyle," "It prepared me for clinical practice," and "It increased my confidence in caring for myself." Lower-rated outcomes clustered in a spiritual/emotional support domain: "It gave me confidence in addressing patients' spiritual concerns," "It contributed to my spiritual growth," and "It gave me comfort in dealing with patients' emotional issues." Items related to personal health and compassion were mid-range ("helped me improve my health" and "helped me sustain my health").

Table 3: Training Outcomes; Analytic n = 303, sorted by mean from high to low

Item	Not My Experience	2	3	4	5	6	Exactly My Experience	Mean
It helped me identify the root cause of patients' problems	7	11	22	35	73	68	87	5.34
It gave me confidence in advising patients about diet, nutrition & lifestyle	13	10	28	50	61	72	69	5.07

It prepared me for clinical practice	6	20	27	51	78	65	56	4.96
It improved my interpersonal skills	14	12	28	55	78	63	53	4.89
It improved my communication skills	11	11	35	50	91	55	50	4.86
It increased my confidence in caring for myself	24	11	33	58	70	51	56	4.7
It has helped me sustain my health	24	21	26	55	68	52	57	4.67
It made me more compassionate	24	15	33	65	73	54	39	4.54
It helped me improve my health	29	25	26	61	57	51	54	4.52
It increased my intuition	22	10	12	17	19	21	14	4.04
It gave me comfort in dealing with patients' emotional issues	39	46	50	52	66	29	21	3.76
It contributed to my spiritual growth	136	28	30	43	27	21	18	2.78
It gave me confidence in addressing patients' spiritual concerns	161	37	32	26	28	14	5	2.29

Practice characteristic items are present in table 4. Across retained items, the average item mean was 4.8. Highest-endorsed items centered on clinical judgment and autonomy. Items reflecting time/meaning were mid-to-high: "Helping patients tell their stories has therapeutic benefit" and "I frequently use physical modalities to provide symptom relief." Work-life items were moderate: "I enjoy good work-life balance" and "I'm comfortable with my financial situation." Lower means concentrated on burden and biomedical testing or other adjuncts: "I often feel exhausted from this work," "I typically rely on laboratory tests and/or imaging studies to make a diagnosis," and "I frequently rely on nutritional supplements in patient care."

Table 4: Practice Characteristics; Analytic n = 282, sorted by mean from high to low

Item	Not at All Like Me	2	3	4	5	6	Exactly Like Me	Mean
Clinical practice brings me great satisfaction	1	3	7	24	45	79	123	5.97
I primarily rely on the history and physical exam to make an assessment	2	5	7	23	36	90	119	5.95
I'm able to recommend treatments or offer guidance to resolve most patient symptoms	1	0	6	12	65	104	94	5.94
I am able to give my patients the time they need	0	4	6	21	59	107	85	5.82
I have enough professional autonomy	2	5	9	25	53	87	100	5.79

I have control over my work schedule	7	15	4	23	41	67	125	5.76
I am confident in my abilities to manage lifestyle-related conditions	1	6	9	23	57	96	90	5.76
I'm able to identify the root cause of most patient complaints	1	2	7	27	69	107	68	5.68
I'm often able to change lives	0	7	15	31	66	80	83	5.58
I help my patients learn how to heal themselves	4	5	5	35	74	93	66	5.53
When symptoms don't fit a conventional medical diagnosis, I can still help	3	7	10	42	72	79	69	5.43
I enjoy good work-life balance	5	11	25	38	58	58	87	5.32
I find that helping my patients tell their stories has therapeutic benefit	8	17	20	52	54	70	61	5.06
I frequently use physical modalities to provide symptom relief	19	25	22	29	36	60	91	5.06
I'm comfortable with my financial situation	15	19	36	34	63	63	52	4.8
I routinely offer recommendations for diet/nutrition	15	25	33	43	58	55	53	4.71
I favor non-toxic remedies or natural herbal products in patient care	35	28	25	34	34	60	65	4.58
I often feel exhausted from this work	43	55	49	55	39	26	15	3.46
I typically rely on laboratory tests and/or imaging studies to make a diagnosis	50	58	50	34	35	35	20	3.46
I frequently rely on nutritional supplements in patient care	67	63	49	42	23	12	26	3.11
I struggle to be compassionate	157	75	19	13	12	4	2	1.82

Among our Doctors of Chiropractic (DCs) sample, subluxation orientation (Do not use vs Biomechanical vs Vitalistic) was associated with multiple outcomes. Subluxation definition response values are presented in table 5. For manipulation/adjustment frequency, a substantial positive association with orientation was identified with post-hoc testing indicating greater use of manipulation in treatment plans for DCs with a "Vitalistic" orientation compared to others with a moderate effect size.

Table 5: Subluxation Use/Definition; Subluxation definitions outlined in S1; Analytic n = 298.

Subluxation Definition	n	%
Do Not Use	91	30.5

Biomechanical (modern)	105	35.2
Vitalistic	102	34.2

Subluxation orientation was also inversely related to the proportion of new patients receiving x-rays indicating lower use of x-rays for new patients when DCs have greater biomedical alignment with a moderate effect size. Subluxation orientation was inversely associated with DC education satisfaction with post-hoc tests highlighting greater dissatisfaction with their education from respondents that are more biomedically aligned (moderate effect size). Analyses of orientation are presented in table 6.

Table 6. Subluxation orientation associations within Sample DCs; * denotes statistical significance.

Outcome	Correlation (subluxation definition)	Group differences	Pairwise Group Differences (DSCF)
Manipulation frequency	Spearman $\rho=0.250, p<0.001^*$	Kruskal-Wallis $\chi^2(2)=19.4, p<0.001^*, \epsilon^2=0.065$	Do not use vs Biomechanical: $p=0.021^*$; Do not use vs Vitalistic: $p<0.001^*$; Biomechanical vs Vitalistic: $p=0.170$
New patient spinal x-ray rate	Spearman $\rho=-0.312, p<0.001^*$	Kruskal-Wallis $\chi^2(2)=28.9, p<0.001^*, \epsilon^2=0.098$	Do not use vs Biomechanical: $p=0.025^*$; Do not use vs Vitalistic: $p<0.001^*$; Biomechanical vs Vitalistic: $p=0.007^*$
Education satisfaction	Spearman $\rho=-0.268, p<0.001^*$	Kruskal-Wallis $\chi^2(2)=23.4, p<0.001^*, \epsilon^2=0.079$	Do not use vs Biomechanical: $p=0.001^*$; Do not use vs Vitalistic: $p<0.001^*$; Biomechanical vs Vitalistic: $p=0.381$

In paired comparison, current health did not differ from health before studying. In contrast, current health was related to current stress (Table 7). Subluxation orientation did not relate to self-rated health.

Table 7. Paired comparisons: current health with health before studying, and stress; analytic n = 303.

Comparison	Mean	Wilcoxon test	Effect size
Current health vs Health before	5.82 vs 5.80	Wilcoxon $W=8560, p=0.840$	Rank-biserial $r=0.017$
Current health vs Stress	5.82 vs 4.24	Wilcoxon $W=30734, p<0.001^*$	Rank-biserial $r=0.731$

DISCUSSION

Overall, respondents reported a motivation profile anchored in prosocial and meaning-oriented drivers with comparatively low endorsement of extrinsic and status motives. In our exploratory analysis, practice orientation, operationalized via subluxation definition, was associated with manipulation frequency, new-patient spinal x-ray use, and education satisfaction. Our findings are also consistent with past work that chiropractors can be placed along a biomedical-to-traditional philosophy continuum with distinct patterns of practice across the continuum. (17-19)

Our DC motivation profile extends, and largely agrees with, earlier student-focused work showing altruism, meaning, and holistic interests as leading reasons for entering chiropractic training. (9) By documenting the item-level distributions in practicing chiropractors, our results move beyond student samples and clarify which motives remain salient into practice. In addition, high endorsement of intellectual and biomedical interests is consistent with reports that chiropractic learners and clinicians express positive attitudes toward EBP and can benefit from explicit EBP instruction during training. (13-16) However, we find that items like “self-healing” do not score highly in chiropractors, in contrast to other complementary health professions. (5,6,27) Respondents in our sample reported high satisfaction, strong autonomy, and sufficient time with patients, alongside heavy reliance on history and physical examination and comparatively low reliance on routine labs, imaging and supplements. This pattern is consistent with prior reports of high job satisfaction among chiropractors (28) and with qualitative descriptions that the “best aspects” of chiropractic include helping patients and transforming quality of life. (29)

Bearing in mind that practice orientation was captured by a single subluxation-definition item serving as a pragmatic proxy, the within-profession orientation signals we observed in our sample, such as greater manipulation frequency and higher x-ray proportions among respondents identifying with a “vitalistic” philosophical orientation, and lower values among “Do not use” and biomechanical/modern respondents, maps conceptually onto ongoing discussions in the chiropractic literature, and within the profession as a whole, about appropriate imaging and evidence-aligned care. (17-19) Contemporary clinical guidance consistently recommends against routine spinal imaging in the absence of red flags, a principle endorsed by the

Canadian Chiropractic Guideline Initiative (30), Choosing Wisely recommendations (31,32), and mirrored in the American College of Radiology Appropriateness Criteria for low back pain. (33) Our subgroup differences in x-ray use are therefore directionally consistent with broader guideline emphasis on selective imaging and may reflect how practice orientation shapes clinical thresholds for ordering tests. It should be noted, however, that imaging decisions in real-world practice are also shaped by structural and system-level factors beyond professional ideology that were not captured in this survey and that likely contribute to variability in imaging rates independent of practice orientation. Future work should examine whether education or quality-improvement interventions that emphasize guideline-concordant imaging can narrow these differences.

The inverse association between biomedical alignment and education satisfaction is one of the more theoretically interesting findings of our dataset. Several explanations merit consideration. First, a curriculum-practice mismatch may be at play. Chiropractic programs, due in part to national board examination content, have historically integrated traditional philosophy alongside biomedical and evidence-based content, and practitioners who ultimately adopt a biomedical orientation may have found this emphasis misaligned with the practice model they came to favor. Prior work linking teaching institution to downstream practice characteristics among Canadian DCs supports this interpretation, suggesting that training context shapes professional orientation in meaningful ways. (20) Second, generational and cohort effects may contribute as practitioners who trained in earlier eras when traditional models were more dominant may have had fewer EBP-integrated learning experiences. This could produce lower satisfaction among those who now favor a biomedical approach and retrospectively perceive their training as insufficiently evidence-aligned. Third, ongoing tension around evidence-based practice integration within chiropractic education, as documented in surveys of chiropractic students and practitioners in multiple countries, may mean that biomedically aligned practitioners perceive a persistent gap between guideline-concordant care and what they were formally trained to do. (13-16) Next, while the directionality of this association cannot be established from a cross-sectional design, it is equally plausible that lower education satisfaction preceded or contributed to a biomedical orientation, rather than following from it. Practitioners who found traditional-philosophy-heavy curricula unsatisfying may have subsequently gravitated toward a more biomedical

identity as a corrective response. Finally, biomedically aligned chiropractors in our sample may evaluate their training against a different reference standard than their vitalistic counterparts. (34) Greater professional contact with physicians, physical therapists, and other allied health providers could change the bar against which chiropractic education is retrospectively judged by respondents, independent of any objective difference in training quality. These interpretations are speculative and limited by the cross-sectional, self-report design of our current sample. Prospective studies tracking satisfaction across training cohorts and institutional contexts would be needed to disentangle these explanations. Nonetheless, prior work demonstrates that EBP-targeted curricular reforms can improve knowledge, attitudes, and self-assessed skills in chiropractic programs (14), and our findings suggest that a renewed focus on evidence-aligned training may have particular salience for improving satisfaction among biomedically oriented practitioners.

The patterns we observe with high intrinsic, prosocial motives, and lower status-seeking differs from motivational profiles often reported in medical student literature, where job security, income, prestige, and family influence commonly feature alongside altruism and scientific interest. (4) The contrast is informative because the quality of motivation (intrinsic vs. extrinsic) is associated with deeper learning, persistence of knowledge, and greater performance in health-profession education. (1) If a chiropractor's motivation profile skews toward autonomous motives, this could be leveraged educationally by coupling meaning and purpose-centric elements with EBP pedagogy to sustain engagement and transfer into practice. Taken all together, what respondents do (history/physical first, selective testing, emphasis on time and autonomy) and what respondents feel prepared to do (clinical reasoning, lifestyle counseling, communication) are coherent and synergistic. Embedding communication training alongside EBP content can leverage the high-autonomy context to improve adherence and patient experience.

We also provide the first examination of self-oriented motives among chiropractors. Our instrument included items such as "heal myself," "grow spiritually," and "improve my health." While such motives are rarely foregrounded in chiropractic papers, they plausibly intersect with clinician well-being and professional identity formation. These are areas linked to performance and persistence in broader health-profession education. Making these motives explicit

can help programs scaffold healthy, ethical integration of personal wellness practices and reflective exercises alongside EBP. A detailed discussion of autonomous motivation within self-determination theory and its relevance to learning and well-being in health professions education is provided by Kusurkar et al. (1)

This study adds several novel elements to the chiropractic literature. One contribution is item-level motivation distributions in a sample of practicing DCs. Prior work emphasized students while we provide a practitioner-level map showing where endorsement concentrates on 7-point scales, enabling more precise curricular and messaging decisions such as in recruitment materials and continuing professional development (CPD) design that highlight meaning, helping others, and intellectual growth. This granularity also facilitates comparisons across subgroups and over time if repeated surveys are used. Also, by tying subluxation orientation to manipulation frequency and x-ray use, we connect identity and ideology markers to tangible behaviors. Given strong, multi-organization guidance to avoid routine imaging for uncomplicated LBP, these subgroup differences are actionable targets for guideline-concordant care efforts.

Two practical implications follow. First, the high autonomy and time signal points to an environment conducive to shared decision-making and therapeutic communication, both of which are associated with better adherence and outcomes across health professions; meta-analytic evidence shows communication training improves adherence substantially. (35) Second, given the low endorsements for items tied to routine testing and adjunctive modalities, stewardship initiatives associated with reducing x-ray use may be well received where they preserve clinician autonomy while reinforcing selective imaging and evidence-aligned pathways for common spine complaints. (30) Audit-and-feedback and point-of-care prompts may harmonize practice patterns (e.g., x-ray ordering thresholds) without forcing a single identity narrative and preserving professional autonomy. Multi-professional collaborations may further normalize evidence-aligned pathways for common spine complaints.

Prior North American studies using probability sampling have described chiropractic subgroups and associations at the population (12,18-20) In contrast, the present study uses a nonprobability, organization-recruited sample to provide fine-grained, item-level distributions across motivations, perceived training outcomes, and practice characteristics within a single

framework. These approaches are complementary as probability sampled surveys are best suited for estimating subgroup prevalence, whereas item-level distributions can be particularly useful for designing and targeting education, professional development, and implementation strategies. (36) Given the nonprobability design, these results are best interpreted as formative, item-level signals to inform priorities rather than population prevalence estimates.

Training outcomes were strongest in clinical reasoning, lifestyle counseling, preparation for practice, and communication/interpersonal skills, and weaker in spiritual/emotional support competencies. This mirrors chiropractic education studies in which EBP-infused curricula improved knowledge, attitudes, and self-assessed skills (14) and practice surveys showing favorable EBP attitudes but modest skill uptake and use, suggesting room for targeted reinforcement in CPD and at the point of care. Our lifestyle-counseling confidence finding also resonates with broader conservative-care guidance for spine conditions, where education and self-management are central for patient outcomes. Our results reinforce that respondent chiropractors are well positioned to support these elements. In contrast, our observed lower ratings for spiritual and emotional support are not unique to chiropractic. Across health-professions education, multiple reviews and consensus statements note limited routine preparation for spiritual care and variable implementation despite its relevance to whole-person care. (37,38)

Limitations

This study has several limitations. First, the sample was a convenience sample recruited through professional organizations, so the results may not represent all chiropractors. Because the survey link was shared through third parties and we did not have recipient counts, we could not calculate a response rate or assess nonresponse bias. Second, the survey was in English only, which may have reduced participation from French-speaking chiropractors in Canada or Spanish-speaking chiropractors in Puerto Rico. Although this was a North American survey, most respondents were from the United States; we retained the smaller Canadian subset to keep the study aligned with its stated scope, but the findings should be interpreted as primarily reflecting U.S. respondents. Third, all practice behaviors were self-reported and could not be verified, and responses may be influenced by recall error or social desirability. Additionally, practice orientation was operationalized using a single subluxation-definition

item as a pragmatic proxy; this is not a validated ideological scale, and professional identity is multi-dimensional and not fully captured by this single item. Readers should interpret orientation-based subgroup differences with this constraint in mind. Finally, the study was cross-sectional without adjustment for multiple comparisons, so results are descriptive and cannot support causal conclusions; differences may also reflect unmeasured factors (e.g., payer constraints, access to imaging).

CONCLUSION

In this cross-sectional sample, chiropractor respondents reported predominantly prosocial, meaning-oriented motivations, strong training outcomes in clinical reasoning, communication, and lifestyle counseling, and practice patterns marked by autonomy, adequate visit time, and reliance on history and physical examination over routine tests. Orientation along a biomedical-to-traditional continuum tracked behavior: "Vitalistic" respondents reported greater manipulation and higher new-patient x-ray use, whereas biomedical aligned "do not use" respondents reported lower x-ray use and lower satisfaction with their education. Within our sample, these signals point to pairing purpose-driven recruitment and curricula with rigorous EBP and communication training, and to imaging stewardship to reduce unwarranted variation. Findings are limited by nonprobability sampling, self-report, and cross-sectional design. Future probability and longitudinal studies should test whether tailored EBP/stewardship interventions improve patient-centered outcomes.

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CONFLICTS OF INTERESTS

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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Supplement 1: Survey Instrument

Motivation for Chiropractic Medicine Study

Introduction

This study seeks to better understand why people train in Chiropractic Medicine and the possible impact of that training and current clinical practice on health and well-being. The findings will be compared to similar data on individuals who chose to study conventional medicine and other healing arts. The study has been reviewed by the Institutional Review Board at the University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill. Completing this anonymous questionnaire signifies your consent to be part of this research. It takes about 6 minutes.

Screening Questions

Q01. Are you practicing Chiropractic Medicine at least part-time?

Response options: No / Yes

Demographics

Q1.3. In what country are you located?

Response options: United States / Canada / Other

Q1.2. Is your practice located in a rural area? [Displayed if Active Practice = Yes]

Response options: No / Yes

Q1.9. Your gender identity

Response options: Male / Female / Other / Prefer not to say

Q1.11. How old are you now?

Response: Dropdown (21-100)

Q1.12. How old were you when you began studying Chiropractic Medicine?

Response: Dropdown (18-80)

Health

Q2.1. How would you rate your current state of health?

7-point scale: Very Poor / Poor / Fair / Fairly Good / Good / Very Good / Excellent

Q2.2. How would you have rated your health prior to enrolling in Chiropractic medical school?

7-point scale: Very Poor / Poor / Fair / Fairly Good / Good / Very Good / Excellent

Q2.3. Do you agree with the statement: Stress is a big problem for me now

7-point scale: Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Somewhat Disagree / Neutral / Somewhat Agree / Agree / Strongly Agree

Motivation and Training

Q3.1. Rate these factors in relation to your decision to become a Chiropractic physician

7-point scale: 1 = Not Important to 7 = Most Important

Items (presented in randomized order): Unable to gain entry to medical school; Intellectual stimulation; Make a positive impact on my community; Prior experience with illness; Potential to make a difference in the world; Interest in science; Meaningful work; Prestige; Social status; Job security; Potential for flexible work hours; Financial security; Gain a deep understanding of health; Help family or friends; Help others; Heal myself; Stay healthy; Improve my health; Make better choices in diet, nutrition, lifestyle, etc.; Grow spiritually; Good income potential; Potential for teaching; Potential to do research; Influence of a trusted authority, spiritual leader, etc.; Influence of a role model; Potential for professional independence; Influence of family/friends; Less physically demanding work; A "calling" or inner awakening; Prior experience with Chiropractic medicine; Change or develop a career; Interest in complementary or integrative medicine; Dissatisfaction with conventional medicine

Q3.2. How satisfied were you with your Chiropractic education?

7-point scale: Very dissatisfied / Dissatisfied / Somewhat dissatisfied / Somewhat satisfied / Satisfied / Very satisfied / Thrilled

Q3.3. How well do these statements describe your education and training in Chiropractic Medicine?

7-point scale: 1 = Not my experience to 7 = Exactly my experience

Items (presented in randomized order): It helped me improve my health; It increased my confidence in caring for myself; It helped me identify the root cause of patients' problems; It has helped me sustain my health; It contributed to my spiritual growth; It made me more compassionate; It improved my communication skills; It improved my interpersonal skills; It gave me confidence in advising patients about diet, nutrition & lifestyle; It gave me confidence in addressing patients' spiritual concerns; It gave me comfort in dealing with patients' emotional issues; It prepared me for clinical practice

Chiropractic-Specific Items

Q15.1. What proportion of your patient visits involve chiropractic manipulation?

Response options: <20% / 20-40% / 40-60% / 60-80% / >80%

Q15.2. Chiropractic Specialty Certifications (check all that apply)

Response options: Chiropractic Acupuncture / Forensic / Internal Medicine / Neurology / Nutrition / Occupational Health / Orthopedics/Neuromuscular Medicine / Pediatrics / Radiology / Rehabilitation / Sports Medicine / None

Q15.3. Which statement best describes how you define chiropractic subluxation?

Response options: (1) "A misalignment of the vertebrae, which interferes with nerve function and innate healing, leading to dis-ease" [Vitalistic] (2) "A functional spinal joint dysfunction that may contribute to pain or impaired movement" [Biomechanical/Modern] (3) "I don't use the term 'subluxation'" [Do not use]

Q15.4. What proportion of new patients receive spinal x-rays?

Response options: <20% / 20-40% / 40-60% / 60-80% / >80%

Current Practice

Q5.1-Q5.12. Practice characteristics items assessed new patient volume, visit time, telehealth use, hours worked, and practice ownership.

Q5.12. Do you agree with the following statements about your clinical practice?

7-point scale: 1 = Not at all like me to 7 = Exactly like me

Items (presented in randomized order): I'm able to identify the root cause of most patient complaints; I'm able to recommend treatments or offer guidance to resolve most patient symptoms; I give prescription drugs to most patients; I'm often able to change lives; I help my patients learn how to heal themselves; Clinical practice brings me great satisfaction; When symptoms don't fit a conventional medical diagnosis, I can still help; I am confident in my abilities to manage lifestyle-related conditions; I routinely offer recommendations for diet/nutrition; I often feel exhausted from this work; I am able to give my patients the time they need; I have enough

professional autonomy; I have control over my work schedule; I'm comfortable with my financial situation; I enjoy good work-life balance; I frequently rely on nutritional supplements in patient care; I favor natural herbal products or other non-toxic remedies; I typically rely on laboratory tests and/or imaging studies to make a diagnosis; I primarily rely on the history and physical exam to make a diagnosis; I find that helping my patients tell their stories has therapeutic benefit; I frequently use physical modalities to provide symptom relief; I struggle to be compassionate

Note: The complete Qualtrics survey instrument printout is available from the corresponding author upon request. Items were presented in randomized order within blocks using Qualtrics adaptive display logic.